

**ELECTRODEPOSITION OF LEAD ON BASE METALS.
PART I. BEHAVIOUR OF ALKALINE BATHS
WITH IRON CATHODES AT LOW
CURRENT DENSITIES.**

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A method for the electrodeposition of lead by using moderately concentrated solutions of litharge in aqueous alkali, the effects of current density, temperature, addition agents and intermediate coating of metallic antimony have been studied.

The wide and increasing demand for lead coated wares in war and especially in industrial practice has stimulated considerable work for obtaining smooth and coherent deposits of lead. The methods at present in vogue are (i) the hot dipping process, (ii) spraying, and (iii) electrodeposition. Despite the apparent simplicity and directness of the technique involved in (i) and (ii), they suffer from the disadvantage that the coating is not always uniform and the deposit not firm and adherent all over. This leads to small cracks and air inclusions especially in (ii) which necessitates the use of a blast of air or of some other gas, which exposes the protected material to outside action. This factor is obviously of very great importance in the case of lead coated wares which are used for stocking acids and similar reagents of common occurrence in numerous chemical industries, *e.g.*, in lead fittings of storage batteries. A limitation also obtains in (ii) since deposition by spraying depends to an appreciable extent on the specific nature of the material to be coated. These difficulties are comparatively absent in (iii), since the rate of lead deposition can be made as small as possible; receptacles with engraving or indents are coated more easily by (iii) than by (i) and (ii). Among the methods for the electrodeposition of lead, the use of acid baths using solutions of a nitrate, acetate, lactate, perchlorate, fluosilicate or a fluoborate is notable. Comparatively satisfactory results have been obtained, however, with the last three substances. An important circumstance observed in this connection is that the concentration of the acid determines very appreciably the nature of the deposit as also the influence of secondary reactions. Thus for example, Smith (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 1287) found that lead which is deposited first as a metal on the cathode is gradually dissolved on prolonged electrolysis and is deposited as the peroxide on the anode. Schuchet (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1883, 22, 488) found that lead is precipitated from strongly acid solutions principally as peroxide on the anode, whereas

from feebly acid solutions, the deposits contain, besides the peroxide, an appreciable proportion of the metal. A method based on this observation has been developed recently in these Laboratories for the quantitative estimation of lead from the anodic deposit of peroxide which will be published shortly. These results have been confirmed by the data obtained in the case of the fluoborate, fluosilicate and perchlorate baths (Fisher, Thiebee and Maxted, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1910, **67**, 347; Blum, Liscomb, Jencks and Baily, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1919, **34**, 101; Blum and Haring, *ibid.*, 1921, **40**, 287; Betts, "Lead Refining by Electrolysis", New York, 1908; Mathers, *Chem. Z.*, 1910, **34**, 1316, 1350; *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1914 **17**, 261) which admit of high current densities and give satisfactorily dense deposits. The principal drawback, however, is that the cost of maintaining these baths is high and at times almost prohibitive. Any reduction in the concentration of the acids leads to the so-called 'tree' formation which is a defect of frequent occurrence in lead deposits produced electrolytically. With the exception of the pioneering work of Glaser (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1900, **7**, 383) and others who have used plumbates, double cyanides, and other alkaline solutions, our knowledge regarding utilisation of alkaline baths for lead plating is meagre. The present work was undertaken with a view to study the conditions of lead deposition using moderately concentrated solutions of litharge, a material which is by no means expensive, in aqueous alkali. The effect of the following factors has been studied: the current density, temperature, separation, (*i.e.* inter-electrode distance), influence of addition agents such as gelatin, antimony and thallium salts and lastly intermediate coating of metallic antimony.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The main composition of the electrolytic bath used in the following experiments was 9.38 g. of litharge (PbO) and 43.5 g. of caustic soda per litre of the aqueous solution. The condition of the electrode surface prior to electrolysis was found to be an important factor. The anode was always a well-cleaned plate of lead of size 6 × 3 cm. approximately. A thin iron plate (7 × 5 cm.) served as the cathode. It was first rendered free from grease by keeping it in a 10 % caustic soda solution for half an hour (*vide infra*) and then washing it with water; it was next immersed in 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid to remove surface scales and rust, well washed with water and rubbed with sand, when a bright surface was obtained; it was

finally washed with distilled water and introduced into the bath solutions. It was further cleaned by 'pickling' with moderately concentrated nitric acid. While this greatly brightened the surface, its activity as an electrode was found to be low, presumably due to surface 'passivation'.

The electrolysis was carried out in a small glass trough fitted inside another containing water and the whole was immersed in a water-bath, during the experiments on the influence of temperature. The trough was fitted with a wooden disc containing slits at appropriate distances through which the electrodes were introduced. In each experiment about 500 c.c. of the plating solution were used. The change in the strength of the solution during electrolysis was small, since very low current densities were used. The solution was filtered after each experiment and was used subsequently in a certain set of experiments. Current was obtained from a storage cell; the circuit included a voltmeter, connected across the electrodes in the bath, a sliding resistance and a precision type milliammeter. Results given in Table I refer to current densities varying from 0.100 to 0.668 amp. per sq. dcm. passed during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. to $3\frac{1}{2}$ hrs. in baths some of which contained a couple of drops of a freshly prepared dilute solution of gelatin in water. Table II shows the influence of temperature on lead plating in the range 17° - 70° .

TABLE I.

P. D. = 0.2 volt. Temp. = 18°. Inter-electrode distance = 3 cm.		Cathode = 5 cm. $\times$ 3 cm.		
No.	I.	C. D.	Time. Addition agent.	Remarks.
1.	15 m. amp.	0.100 amp./dcm ² .	45 min. ...	Density of deposit very poor.
2.	18	0.120	1 hr. ...	" " "
3.	25	0.166	1 hr. ...	" " "
4.	30	0.200	1 hr. ...	" " "
5.	15	0.100	1 hr. 2 drops of gelatin.	Initial 'pickling' with nitric acid deleted. Deposit coherent and greyish white; tended to improve by increasing C D.
6.	20	0.132	1 hr.	" " " "
7.	25	0.166	1 hr.	" " " "
8.	30	0.200	3 $\frac{1}{2}$ hr.	" " " "
9.	50	0.334	2 hr.	Not 'pickled' with nitric acid P. D. raised to 0.25 volt. 'Tree' formation sets in which increased with C D.
10.	60	0.400	2 hr.	" " " "
11.	65	0.434	$\frac{1}{2}$ hr.	" " " "
12.	1000	0.666	$\frac{1}{2}$ hr.	A central cathode (not 'pickled' was used between two anodes. Separation between cathode and either anode 2 cm. The deposit was good.

TABLE II.

P. D. = 0.3 volt. C. D. = 0.666 amp./dcm.² Inter-electrode distance = 2½ cm. Size of plates = 5 cm. × 3 cm.

No.	Time.	Temp.	Addition Agent	Remarks.
1.	1 hr.	20°	Two drops of gelatin solution.	Deposit tended to "peel"
2.	2 hr.	30°	" " "	" "
3.	2 hr.	40°	" " "	Deposit more firm and dense,
4.	2 hr.	50°	" " "	"
5.	½ hr.	50°	A small pinch of anti-mony oxide is also added.	Deposit poor, "tree" formation sets in early.
6.	1 hr.	17°	Four drops of 1% tartar emetic soln. also added.	"Free" formation absent; deposit improved.
7.	1 hr.	22°	" " "	Further improvement in the deposit.
8.	1½ hr.	35°	" " "	" " "
9.	1 hr.	60°	Two more drops of tartar emetic solution added.	"Treeing" after an hour; deposit to peel off at the edges where "treeing" was maximum.
10.	1 hr.	70°-72°	" " "	"Treeing" commenced in about ¾ hour.

R E S U L T S .

It is seen from the results in Table I that at a constant bath temperature, an increase in the current density (C. D.) improves the quality of the deposit. There is, however, an optimum value at about 0.334 amp./sq. dcm. (I , current used = 50 milliamps.), any further increase in C. D. induces 'treeing' and looseness of deposit. A much higher C. D. could, however, be employed with distinct advantage with a cathode midway between two anodes and a smaller separation. It was observed that the cathodic deposit was almost entirely restricted to the side opposite to the anode. The denseness as also the total amount of the deposit increased when the cathode was rotated so as to expose either of its sides towards the anode. This was

particularly so when placed in the centre (No. 12). These experiments also showed that the addition of a few drops of a dilute solution of gelatin in water had a decisive influence in improving the deposit. Partly similar results were obtained by Mathers (*loc. cit.*) who found that the addition of very small amounts of peptone and olive oil yielded fine grained lead deposits directly on steel surfaces from fluoborate baths which are perhaps the most convenient and economic amongst the acidic baths for lead plating.

It was also observed that the coating was better if the bath was agitated during electrolysis by carefully bubbling a stream of air. This was adopted in all subsequent experiments. Table II shows the influence of temperature on the electrodeposition. It is seen that at constant current density the quality of the deposit improves by increasing the temperature upto a certain extent (about 50°) and deteriorates at higher temperatures. It was also observed during these experiments that the addition of only a few drops of a dilute emetic solution of tartar had a very beneficial effect on the growth of the lead deposit. It is important that the addition agent should be well miscible with the plating solution. It was observed, for instance, that despite its antimony content (No. 5) the addition of a small pinch of antimony oxide was of no avail in reducing the 'tree' formation. Experiments were also made under similar conditions with potassium tartrate and gelatin as addition agents (Nos. 9, 10). *Treeing* set in fairly soon after the commencement of electrolysis. This shows that the efficacy observed in the case of tartar emetic is to be attributed principally to the dissolved antimony in the bath. Evidence has been adduced by Joshi and Padmanabhan J. *Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 178) in that an addition agent influences appreciably the electrodeposit by increasing the rate of *nuclei* formation precedent to the crystal growth on the electrode. In view of the wide range of composition and ease with which antimony and lead alloy together, it was thought that a preliminary coating of antimony on the cathode might yield a denser and an unpealable deposit of lead. Results similar to this have been obtained by A. G. Betts (*loc. cit.*) in lead deposition from fluosilicate baths for plating storage battery fittings, where a preliminary deposit of copper has been found necessary.

In order to produce a preliminary coating of antimony, the need was observed for a yet cleaner and more burnished cathode surface. '*Pickling*' with concentrated nitric acid imparted an apparently increased brightness, but the method was not used for reasons indicated already. '*Electrolytic pickling*' gave very satisfactory results. The iron plate was made the cathode in a bath of hot dilute (6*N*) sulphuric acid, which was electrolysed for about ha

an hour. It was then carefully washed with water and electrolysed for about an hour as a cathode, in an *alkali bath* containing sodium carbonate (43 g.), caustic soda (17 g.), sodium phosphate (13 g.) per litre of aqueous solution. The plate was then well washed with distilled water and '*pickled*' for a few minutes in dilute sulphuric acid (1 part of acid to 15 parts water by weight). It was washed with boiling water and then dipped in a mixture containing (by weight) concentrated nitric acid (75 parts), concentrated sulphuric acid (100 parts), and sodium chloride (1 part), for a few seconds, and finally well washed with hot water (*cf.* "Theoretical and Applied Electrochemistry" by Thomson, p. 181). It was made the cathode and was electrolysed at 220 in a small bath containing 1.5% tartar emetic solution with a drop of gelatin, which gave the necessary preliminary coating of antimony in about 1½ hour. This piece was next made the cathode in a lead plating solution (0.25 volt. 100 milliamp. 0.667 amp. per sq. dcm separation 2½-3 hours, 60°.) This gave lead coats which were firmer and of greater thickness than those obtained during any of the previous experiments. Furthermore, it was observed that the addition of small amounts of gelatin and tartar emetic and interrupting the electrolysis for a brief time after every half an hour improved greatly the quality of the cathode deposit and eliminated *tree ing.* Very satisfactory results were also obtained by the use of small quantities of solutions of *thallium carbonate*.

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